

STEM FOR FUN

Mairéad Holden

St. Teresa's Primary School, Balbriggan, Co. Dublin

STEM education has become a hot topic, to the point where it has been described as an area of “universal preoccupation” (English, 2016). However, equality of access to STEM Education and STEM careers is not universal. Lack of access to STEM Education and careers is especially challenging for struggling learners in DEIS settings. The STEM for Fun project explored the effectiveness of a small-group DEIS-centric programme designed to develop primary pupils’ engagement, critical thinking skills and language using STEM-based activities over a six-week period. This paper reports on one of the aspects of the STEM for FUN project: pupils’ engagement. The project was undertaken in a DEIS Band 2 Urban primary school in North County Dublin with three 4th class pupils, all of whom were categorised as “struggling learners” according to their performance in standardised Maths and English tests. Analysis of data suggests that the STEM for Fun intervention had a positive effect on participants’ engagement in STEM learning and that the STEM for Fun tasks also supported the development of positive learning dispositions.

INTRODUCTION

STEM for Fun is an intervention which formed part of a small scale participatory action research project, designed to promote engagement, critical thinking skills and STEM language. The intervention was designed in response to the needs of a small group of pupils I had been working with in my own classroom context. These pupils were deemed “struggling learners” having scored below the 10th percentile in their most recent Maths and English standardised tests. I was troubled by my pupils’ low confidence, lack of motivation and negative learning dispositions. STEM for Fun aimed to capitalise on the success of the DEIS programme “Maths for Fun”. This programme had been effective at addressing engagement and confidence in Maths within my own school and its effectiveness in other DEIS schools had been noted in existing literature (DES, 2011; Weir, Archer, O’Flaherty & Gilleece, 2011). Recent literature pertaining to STEM in Irish education suggests a need for innovative projects which promote “engagement, enjoyment and excellence in STEM learning” (STEM Education Review Group, 2016). Aside from content-related aspects of STEM, recent research also underlines the importance of developing 21st century skills, referred to as “the 5 C’s”: creativity, communication, collaboration, cooperation and critical thinking (Dede, 2010; Butler, 2014). I wondered could STEM for FUN weave all of these aspects together, in order to support the learner needs I had identified?

LITERATURE REVIEW

In terms of supporting pupils’ engagement and confidence, I examined research relating to the development of positive dispositions (as described by Katz, 1993). She defines a disposition as “an enduring habit of mind and action or a tendency to respond to situations in characteristic ways. A productive disposition in STEM is an aspect of STEM Proficiency. It involves pupils seeing STEM as useful and relevant, practical and enjoyable, engaging and motivating; recognising the benefits of perseverance and developing confidence in STEM knowledge and ability. While teachers may aspire to develop productive dispositions in their pupils, FitzPatrick, Twohig and Morgan (2014) also flag that learning dispositions is a priority area as identified by parents of primary school pupils.

While reflections documented in my reflective diary suggested my pupils were struggling with negative dispositions and lack of engagement, I looked to literature to guide me in how I might document the development of pupil dispositions in a more structured manner. While frameworks relating to dispositions exist in early years and post-primary curricula (NCCA, 2009; 2015) a review of existing literature revealed a gap in relation to dispositions from 2nd to 6th class. The STEM for Fun project would involve design of a draft dispositions framework to ameliorate this.

While I had considered the area of dispositions from the perspective of teachers and parents, I had not taken cognisance of my pupils' views. I explored literature for ways to give my pupils the opportunity to have their voices heard as well as reflect on and take ownership of their own learning. Baird, Fensham, Gunstone and White (1993) suggest the usefulness of reflective response slips as a tool to capture pupil voice and support reflection, which can also contribute to the development of metacognition. The main idea behind such pupil reflection is that

...the meaning any learner derives from a lesson depends on number of factors: the person's attitudinal state, perception of the nature, purpose and progress of the lesson, existing knowledge, and decisions about what to do as learning proceeds... Attitudes, abilities and knowledge are all involved in the processing of information

(Baird et al, 1993, p.63).

In addition to documenting dispositions, I wondered what kinds of tasks would be most appropriate and effective in developing and enhancing them. The low-threshold high-ceiling (LTHC) nature of the Maths for Fun activities was a key contributory factor in developing pupil engagement (Boaler, 2016; DES, 2011). LTHC tasks, as described by McClure, Woodham and Borthwick, (2011) are tasks which are accessible enough for all levels of pupils to experience an initial degree of success, but also present additional layers of sophistication for pupils who require extra challenge. Teachers and their pupils reported that the open-ended nature of Maths for Fun tasks also fostered confidence and engagement, as pupils had the opportunity to explore activities from multiple perspectives (DES, 2011).

A further effective feature of Maths for Fun tasks was their hands-on nature. This resonates with the constructionist principles as described by Papert (1987). While "fun" was important to engage pupils and build confidence, "hard fun" using meaningful hands-on tasks where pupils got the opportunity to manipulate different materials served to help pupils' development of Science, Technology, Engineering and Maths concepts.

OVERVIEW OF THE STEM FOR FUN INTERVENTION

The STEM for Fun programme involved a six-week intervention incorporating a variety of hands-on STEM-based activities arranged by theme: Electronics; Robotics; Shapes and Patterns; Engineering and Forces; Coding and Digital Presentation skills. Themes had a cross-curricular focus incorporating elements of Digital Technology, Language, Science, Maths, Visual Arts and SPHE. Each 45 minute lesson concluded with a short reflective discussion using reflective response slips. The final week of the programme involved the pupil participants presenting, demonstrating and explaining an activity of their choice to their classmates, using a Google Slides presentation.

METHODOLOGY

The STEM for Fun project was conducted within the paradigm of participatory action research (Groundwater-Smith, Dockett & Bottrell, 2015; McNiff, 2002), through generating a personal living educational theory. Whitehead (1989, p.41) describes living educational

theory as “an explanation produced by an individual for their educational influence in their own learning, in the learning of others and in the learning of the social formation in which they live and work”. Whitehead articulates the challenge presented when we find ourselves living in contradiction to our values. I identify care (as described by Noddings, 1992) and social justice (as described by Bernstein, 2000) as values which underpin my work as an educator. The lack of engagement of my pupils due to their low confidence and negative dispositions conflicted with my values. I felt compelled to act to support these pupils, with the aim of developing their agency as STEM learners.

The STEM for Fun intervention occurred in partnership and dialogue (as described by Groundwater-Smith et al, 2015) with my pupils, rather than an externally imposed study, done “to” them. This allowed reflexivity (as described by Brookfield, 2002) where I amended my practice in response to my own, my pupils and my colleague’s reflections. Data collection methods were chosen to reflect and respect the voice of the pupils, and their perceived progress in their learning.

Rigour and Potential Bias

To enhance the rigour of the study, I used a combination of data collection tools: Reflective diary, pupil reflective response slips, semi-structured interviews, attitude questionnaires and I also invited a colleague to act as critical friend. Due to the nature and design of the study, it was open to the effects of various biases. These included acquiescence and the Hawthorne effect. My critical friend helped to limit confirmation bias through our engagement in professional dialogue and through her observation of some of the STEM for Fun activities in action.

Dispositions Framework

In order to assess and track dispositions identified during pre- and post- semi-structured interviews, I developed a Dispositions Assessment rubric (See Figure 1) drawing from existing Aistear and Junior Cycle frameworks as well as drawing from the work of Deakin-Crick, Broadfoot & Claxton, (2004).

Frequency→ Disposition↓	Rarely	Occasionally	Regularly	Almost Always	Always
Curiosity Questions the world around them. Seeks answers to questions posed by self and/or others.					
Perseverance Makes continued effort to work towards a solution despite challenges.					
Confidence <i>(Have a go attitude)</i> Approaches tasks through thinking or doing without hesitation					
Self-Awareness of Learning Can self-identify strengths & needs related to their own learning.					
Resourcefulness Can find appropriate solutions to problems.					
Meaning Making Connects new STEM ideas or information and prior knowledge. Uses STEM to make sense of their world.					

Figure 1. Dispositions Rubric (Adapted from Deakin-Crick, Broadfoot & Claxton (2004); NCCA (2009; 2015).

Pupil reflective response slips

After each STEM for Fun session, pupils were asked to complete a short response slip with a number of question stems and incomplete sentences (McKernan, 1996). The questions used in the response slip were adapted for the primary STEM context from those used by Baird et al. (1993) whose work related to Science specifically. The pupil response slips not only acted as qualitative data but also served as a valuable formative and self-assessment tool. They allowed me to track pupil attitudes, pupil learning and pupil perceptions of my teaching. The response slips also provided an important record of pupils' use of STEM language.

DATA ANALYSIS

For the purpose of this paper, data analysis relating to engagement and dispositions will be presented.

Engagement

Data emerged across qualitative sources, showing the development of pupils' engagement in and enthusiasm for STEM for Fun and STEM in general. The STEM for Fun pupil group regularly asked "Can we stay in to work on this at break time?" (Reflective diary, 01/02/17). Pupils in the STEM for Fun group stated that they "liked" or in some cases "loved" activities. They even stated this in instances where they also stated that activities were difficult. In fact, the pupils were so engaged and enthusiastic, not only did they stay in over break time (at their own request) but they also brought the activities home to work on them.

Pupil preferences

The STEM for Fun group also selected "Scribblebots" as their topic to present to their classmates. The creative and interactive nature of the Scribblebot activity correlates with data from the attitude questionnaires. Responses from these questionnaires suggest that almost 90% of pupils in 3rd and 4th class enjoy designing and building activities. This was also true for the STEM for Fun group who expressed similar strong preferences for such active STEM learning activities as outlined earlier. Creativity represents one of the 5 C's of 21st Century Skills (Dede, 2010; Butler, 2013) as mentioned earlier. Data suggesting pupils' preference for hands-on activities also correlate with existing literature (Varley, Murphy and Veale, 2008) suggesting that pupils find activities where they get to use the equipment themselves (rather than a teacher demonstration) more engaging.

Making STEM connections

An aspect of engagement requires pupils to make connections between STEM and other areas, for example, with other subjects or with life outside of the classroom including at home. While strong connections were made in some areas, in the case of Science, connections may need reinforcement. Although in their questionnaires, almost 70% of pupils in 3rd and 4th class stated that they viewed Science as useful, this connection with home is not made in the same strong way as Maths and Technology. Almost 90% of pupils reported using Maths and Technology at home, whereas only 41% of pupils stated that they used Science at home.

STEM at home

Pupils in 3rd and 4th class appeared to make strong connections with Maths, Technology and home, according to responses in Pre and Post Attitudes Questionnaires. Pupils who took part in the STEM for Fun intervention also made further connections by bringing their projects home to work on. Sarah asked "Can I bring this home to show my Mam?" when working on her 3-D shape construction task, where she had made a bird structure using straws (Reflective

diary, 7/02/17, week 4). Debbie brought her Scribblebot home one weekend to play with in her Nana's.

“Scribblebots won't work on the carpet, I tried it in my Nana's”. When I asked her what her Nana thought of her Scribblebot, she replied, “My Nana said I'm gonna be off working in NASA someday”.

(Reflective diary, 15/02/17, week 4).

These statements reveal the pupils' interest in bringing their STEM for Fun work home. They talked about it with friends and family, connecting STEM with their daily lives outside the classroom. For example, when Conor was working on circuits during Week One, he remarked, “This is actually kind of handy coz if a bulb goes in your house you can fix it!” (Reflective Diary, 30/01/17, week 1).

DISPOSITIONS

Analysis of data gathered suggested that some dispositions are more susceptible to change than others. Existing literature suggests that a holistic approach involving both home and whole school are effective in developing positive dispositions to learning (Katz, 1993). While a number of findings emerged relating to the various elements which comprise dispositions, for the purpose of this paper, I report on findings relating to dispositions of confidence and perseverance.

Confidence

During interviews, the STEM for Fun pupils were asked a number of questions which related to their perceptions of their own learning. Prior to the intervention, the responses given by the pupils revealed a general lack of self-confidence and lack of self-efficacy in relation to classroom learning. The pupils seemed acutely aware of the gaps in their knowledge. Analysis of data from my diary showed a social dynamic unfolding between the pupils during the intervention. Some of the pupils developed a notable expertise in some activities to the point that they could act as “expert”. I encouraged the more expert pupil to help and support pupils who were finding the task challenging. An example of this was Conor's proficiency at assembling successful circuits. He had created several complex circuits while the other two pupils in the group had not managed to complete the initial basic task. He paused his work on own activities in order to help out the other pupils.

Without prompting, Debbie took up the flashcards [which had STEM vocabulary printed on them] and started helping Conor to say the words. Later in the lesson, Conor helped Debbie and Sarah to assemble their circuits.

(Reflective diary, 30/01/17, week 1).

This extract describes Debbie and Conor acting as “experts”. This was a notable development for these particular pupils who had earlier showed low levels of confidence and motivation. I felt acting as “expert” offered an opportunity for a confidence and self-esteem boost for those pupils. It also allowed the pupils to see each other as sources of information, rather than always relying on the teacher. Acting as experts for each other also demonstrated progress in pupil collaboration and communication. These represent two of the “5 C's” of 21st Century Skills (Dede, 2010; Butler 2014) as described earlier.

Perseverance

Prior to the intervention, the pupils showed low self confidence in Maths was also reported by my critical colleague who was their class teacher. I wondered if the pupils' perception of their “failure” in standardised Maths tests had contributed to their low self-confidence. The people best placed to answer this were the pupils themselves, but I felt it would be inappropriate and

unhelpful to ask the pupils this directly. However, I was able to observe their anxiety when presented with certain types of Maths questions. These I describe as “high-risk” items for the pupils. They had built up a degree of anxiety based on previous failure. Not only had they failed (gotten the wrong answer or not known how to do the question), but they had done so publicly, in front of their classmates. The anxiety which stemmed from such public failure could not be helpful when trying to develop perseverance. This anxiety also appeared deep-rooted and resistant to change.

Today’s session made me realise how unsure of herself Debbie is in general. Has she gotten into a habit of not bothering to think for herself? Has a spoon-feeding approach in learning support exacerbated this? Her [Debbie’s] behaviour today has made me wonder about how dispositions can become quite deep-rooted, and whether something like STEM for Fun alone can really alter such seemingly deep-rooted behaviours.

(Reflective diary, 06/02/17, week 2).

How could I support Debbie to ameliorate and develop her “deep-rooted” lack of perseverance in six weeks? The extract below describes an encounter I had with Debbie whose lack of perseverance was frustrating me and her class teacher. I eventually decided to broach this directly with Debbie herself

I have seen her [Debbie’s] confidence improve during the STEM for Fun sessions. She is no longer “afraid” to handle the materials [wires and batteries] - she was very timid to begin with. I will consult with her class teacher on this and maybe try to push her on to be a bit more autonomous in her sums [high-risk items for Debbie]. I have seen her work independently in other areas- maybe I will highlight this observation to Debbie herself and see if it will make a difference?

(Reflective diary, 6/02/17, week 2).

The above extract also demonstrates the potential of the STEM for Fun activities to develop perseverance at little or no risk of failure, anxiety or humiliation. The “low-risk” nature of the STEM for Fun activities seemed to be more conducive to developing perseverance in the pupils. While the activities had an end goal, such as getting the marble into the pot in tumble tracks, there were many different paths to arrive at the same goal. It was apparent to me from the analysis of the data that the disposition of perseverance is complex. Six weeks is a short time to expect a significant change, but there was some evidence of pupils transferring perseverance to maths sums which they previously would have given up on.

When it came to doing the division sums, she [Debbie] seemed to approach them confidently, looking for minimum assistance from me. Conor, although noticeably tired, worked well and got on with doing his sums. He finished his work [including a difficult item on tally marks which featured a lot of text] without any prompting or pestering from me, a big improvement!

(Reflective diary, 13/02/17, week 3).

Supporting pupil engagement in reflective discussion

The context of the project supported pupils’ engagement in reflective discussion. The pupils had very little prior experience of using reflective discussion. The conversation and discussion around the reflective response slips grew to become a natural habit. The pupils would tidy up their materials and then reconvene to have a “chat” about how the session went. This also demanded a degree of accountability from the pupils, as they knew they would be required to discuss and explain what they had worked on. I felt that my classroom was becoming a place where it was ok to make mistakes, which in turn provided talking points and informed our future action. Sometimes “bits of stuff fall apart” or don’t work the way they’re meant to. In our STEM for Fun group, it was our job to experiment and discuss the “why”. This experimentation was becoming valued and seen by the pupils as providing

opportunities for learning. Research from existing literature supports this “mistake-valuing environment” (as described by Boaler, 2016) as an important factor in further developing pupils’ engagement as well as their critical thinking skills.

SUMMARY OF MAIN FINDINGS, IMPLICATIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

Engagement

The pupil participants demonstrated an increased level of engagement in learning, during and after the intervention. This increased engagement was across learning in general, but particularly in relation to STEM. A possible explanation for this improved engagement may have been hands-on, creative and collaborative nature of STEM for Fun activities. Pupils stated a preference for activities of this nature, both in existing research and in data gathered during the course of this study. This study was conducted in a specific context with a small sample group. Further study in a diverse range of contexts with a large sample would be needed, in order to establish if similar improvements in engagement arising from using STEM for Fun- style approaches could be achieved in different settings. The STEM in Irish Education Report (STEM Education Review Group, 2016) underlined the urgent need for innovative projects which promote engagement, enjoyment and excellence in STEM teaching and learning. STEM for Fun offers a possible intervention to develop such engagement. It also helps pupils and their families, particularly those from a disadvantaged context, to see STEM as useful, relevant and accessible to all. It is a recommendation of this study that the STEM for Fun model be trialled in a variety of school contexts (both DEIS and non-DEIS) in order to ascertain whether similar findings emerge in other contexts.

Positive dispositions

Pupil participants demonstrated an increase in positive dispositions to learning during and following the STEM for Fun intervention. The positive dispositions which showed the greatest increase were curiosity, perseverance and confidence. The “have a go” attitude in relation to Maths has been sustained following conclusion of the intervention. A whole-school approach would help these dispositions to become embedded.

A further finding of this study is that negative dispositions can be deep-rooted. A holistic intervention on a whole-school basis over a longer time-frame along with parental support could help in addressing such negative dispositions.

This study revealed a significant gap in curriculum policy relating to learning dispositions for children from 2nd-6th class. While this study focused on 3rd and 4th class only, this study did identify the important role played by these learning dispositions in supporting pupil learning. It is a recommendation of this study that policy be developed to build a developmentally appropriate dispositions framework for pupils from 2nd- 6th class. To this end, the study presented a possible Dispositions assessment rubric. While used for teacher-led assessment in STEM as part of this project, this rubric could also be adapted for use as a pupil self-assessment tool across multiple subjects.

This study demonstrated the value of reframing mistakes as opportunities for learning in order to build positive dispositions. Such mistakes can offer rich opportunities for discussion and learning, acting as a springboard for learning, in the spirit of formative assessment. This study has also identified the potential of low floor high ceiling tasks to help promote confidence and engagement in struggling learners within my specific school context. I recommend that further study could be conducted into the impact of such activities on the STEM learning of average and above average ability pupils.

REFERENCES

- Baird, J., Fensham, P., Gunstone, R., White, R. in Whitelegg, E. Tresman, S., Thomas, J. (1993). *The importance of reflection in improving science teaching and learning. Challenges and opportunities for science education*. Open University.
- Bernstein, B. B. (2000). *Pedagogy, symbolic control, and identity: Theory, research, critique* (No. 4). Rowman & Littlefield.
- Boaler, J. (2016). *Building a maths mindset community*. Youcubed. University of Stanford.
- Brookfield, S. D. (2002). Using the lenses of critically reflective teaching in the community college classroom. *New directions for community colleges*, 2002(118), 31-38.
- Butler, D. (2014). *Embedding the development and assessment of key skills into lesson design*. Workshop presented at NCCA Assessment for Key Competencies Conference, November 2014.
- Deakin-Crick, R, Broadfoot, P., & Claxton, G. (2004). Developing an effective lifelong learning inventory: The ELLI project. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 11(3), 247-272.
- DES. (2005). *DEIS—Delivering Equality of Opportunity in Schools*. DES.
- DES. (2011). *National Strategy: Literacy and Numeracy for Learning and Life 2011-2019*. DES.
- Dede, C. (2010). Comparing frameworks for 21st century skills. *21st century skills: Rethinking How Students Learn*, 20, 51-76.
- English, L. D. (2016). STEM education K-12: perspectives on integration. *International Journal of STEM education*, 3(1), 3.
- FitzPatrick, S., Twohig, M. & Morgan, M. (2014): Priorities for primary education? From subjects to life-skills and children’s social and emotional development. *Irish Educational Studies*. 33(3), 269-286.
- Groundwater-Smith, S., Dockett, S., Bottrell, D. (2015). *Participatory research with children and young people*. Sage: London
- Katz, L. G. (1993). Dispositions as educational goals. *ERIC Digest*.
- McClure, L., Woodham, L. & Borthwick, A. (2011). Using Low Threshold High Ceiling Tasks. Nrich. University of Cambridge. Retrieved <https://nrich.maths.org/7701/index>
- McKernan, J. (1996). *Curriculum action research: A handbook of methods and resources for the reflective practitioner*. London: Routledge.
- McNiff, J. (2002). *Action research for professional development*.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2009) *Aistear: The early childhood curriculum framework*. Dublin: NCCA.
- NCCA. (2015). *Key Skills of Junior Cycle*. NCCA.
- Noddings, N. (1992). *The challenge to care in schools*. Teachers College Press.
- Papert, S. (1987). Microworlds: transforming education. In *Artificial intelligence and education* (Vol. 1, pp. 79-94). Ablex Utrecht.
- STEM Review Group. (2016). *STEM Education in the Irish School System*. ESRI.
- Varley, J., Murphy, C. & Veale, O. (2008). *Science in primary schools, Phase 2: Final report*. NCCA.
- Weir, S., Archer, P., O’Flaherty, A., & Gilleece, L. (2011). *A report on the first phase of the evaluation of DEIS*. Dublin: Educational Research Centre
- Whitehead, J. (1989). Creating a living educational theory from questions of the kind, ‘How do I improve my practice?’ *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 19(1), 41-52.